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Abstract:	<p>This report outlines the governance framework for data stewardship in BatCAT (Task 4.6). It sets practical rules for handling project data and metadata, complementing schema development (in T4.2), data landscape mapping (in T4.3), and ontology development (in T4.4). The proposed framework defines minimal metadata kernels per record type, a metadata-change workflow, PID management based on Handles system. Integrity and consistency checks are addressed through validation against the BatCAT PID profile. The deliverable emphasises alignment with community recommendations (FAIR, EMMC, RDA).</p>
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Abbreviations and acronyms

W3C	World Wide Web Consortium.
EMMC	European Materials Modelling Council
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FDO	FAIR Digital Object
IRI	Internationalized Resource identifier. Internationalised URI. (RFC 3987)
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SDO	Scientific Data Officer
KI	Kernel Information
JSON-LD	W3C JSON for Linked Data.
DCAT	W3C Data Catalog Vocabulary
MD5	Hash algorithm. (RFC 1321).
PRO-V	W3C Provenance Vocabulary.
SHA	Family of hash algorithms (RFC 4634).
SPDX	Software Package Data Exchange. SPDX 2.2.1 equals ISO/IEC 5962:2021.
ISO 8601	Datetime standard (RFC 3339).
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
DOI	(Crossref) Digital Object Identifier.
UTF-8	Superset of ASCII including additional bytes to encode Unicode characters.

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1. Executive summary

This document provides the first version of the BatCAT data stewardship framework, generated under Task 4.6 - 'Data Stewardship'. The aim is to ensure that data produced and exchanged in the project is managed in a consistent, transparent, and FAIR-compliant way, while keeping the approach practical for all the partners.

The document introduces the roles and workflow for metadata governance (cf. [Sec. 2](#) and [Sec. 4](#)) and PID architecture together with a minimal set of metadata fields agreed through a consortium survey and proposes initial practices for persistent identifiers (Handles/DOIs) and versioning (cf. [Sec. 3](#)) and consistency checks will be supported through validating PIDs against the BatCAT Handle Record Profile (cf. [Sec. 3](#)) to ensure that all records comply with a common rule set.

Overall, this deliverable should be seen as a living governance baseline rather than a fixed rulebook. This is the description of how data stewardship is envisioned at present. It will evolve over the course of the project as partners provide feedback, and it complements related work in WP4 on schemas, metadata landscape, and ontologies.

Accordingly, this document is accompanied by a public GitHub repository (<https://github.com/HE-BatCAT/BatCAT-DataStewardship>) where the agreed (meta)data policies are stored, in markdown format.

All text, from all sources, must be encoded as UTF-8 for processing³.

2. Roles for the governance workflow

To ensure that data stewardship in BatCAT is implemented in a structured and transparent manner, a governance framework has been established. The identified roles (SDO, Data, Platform and Ontology contacts) are described below.

Scientific Data Officer (SDO) – NMBU

NMBU serves as the Scientific Data Officer (SDO) for Task 4.6. This role provides oversight and coordination of BatCAT's data stewardship governance. The SDO is the point of contact for changes that could affect how data and metadata are structured, described, or managed across the consortium. In practice, this means the SDO is responsible for receiving and reviewing change requests related to the metadata schema, the use of persistent identifiers (PIDs), and the rules for data retention.

Every formal change request is reviewed within five working days. If the change is relevant only to a local workflow or documentation, it may be directed to the appropriate partner or platform contact.

³

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/open-standards-for-government/cross-platform-character-encoding-profile>

However, if the change has consequences for the project as a whole, the SDO ensures that it follows the full governance workflow.

The SDO is notified only when a change is considered major, for example, modifications to the agreed kernel attributes (the minimum set of metadata fields required), changes to PID profiles or adjustments that affect the alignment with ontologies developed in Task 4.4. These kinds of changes influence interoperability and long-term data governance and therefore require central review.

When such a request is made, the SDO is responsible for triaging it, consulting with ontology and platform contacts where necessary, and ensuring that the final decision is recorded. All approved major changes are entered into the central decision log, which serves as the authoritative record of BatCAT's data stewardship governance. This process guarantees accountability and provides transparency for both consortium partners and external reviewers.

Data Contacts – Each Partner

Every consortium partner designates a Data Contact for the data they generate, curate, or manage. The role of the Data Contact is to ensure that the agreed minimum metadata kernel is completed for each dataset or digital object contributed to BatCAT. The Data Contact also confirms that retention rules are followed locally, according to the shared Retention Playbook.

Platform Contacts – Technical Partners

Technical partners serving as Platform Contacts are responsible for the implementation of approved changes in the systems used by BatCAT, including eLabFTW, LinkAhead, and the central node. Once a metadata or PID policy change is agreed, Platform Contacts ensure that it is reflected in the operational systems in a timely manner, typically within two weeks of approval.

Ontology Contacts

When a proposed change alters the meaning of a metadata field or raises questions of semantic alignment, the Ontology Contacts are consulted. Their role is to verify that BatCAT's metadata remains consistent with the ontologies being developed in Task 4.4 and with external standards such as EMMO. This ensures long-term interoperability and alignment with the broader materials modelling community.

3. Persistent identifiers and metadata profiles

To make digital object identifiers both human-resolvable and machine-actionable, BatCAT follows architecture that distinguishes

- (i) globally unique persistent identifiers (PIDs);
- (ii) a minimal, machine-actionable record stored with the PID itself
- (iii) domain-rich master metadata in BatCAT's platforms and presented on the PID's landing page.

This is consistent with its community guidelines. Research Data Alliance (RDA) recommends keeping only a small, stable set of attributes in the PID record sufficient for automated decisions at resolution time while richer descriptions remain in external systems and on the landing page (Weigel, et al., 2019). PID kernel Information is a set of mandatory and optional attributes that is stored within a PID record. In parallel, the FAIR Digital Object (FDO) approach frames PID records as profile-governed collections of attributes whose keys and value constraints are registered, so that software can validate and interpret PID records. Concept of PID Kernel Information is implemented through a Handle record profile (FDO Forum, 2024). The BatCAT Handle Record Profile is our PID KI profile.

The BatCAT Handle Record Profile (v0.1)

In BatCAT we implement PID-KI as the BatCAT Handle Record Profile (v0.1), a short public specification registered with its own PID, that lists mandatory attributes for every BatCAT Handle record inspired by RDA PID-KI (see [Annex Table 1](#)). Each BatCAT PID includes a profile pointer to this Profile, and new records are validated against for consistency checks . In other words, the rule set for PID KI are enforced through the BatCAT Handle Record Profile.

Every BatCAT Handle record include at least:

- [21.T11966/FdoProfile](#): PID of the BatCAT Handle Record Profile (v0.1).
- [0.TYPE/URL](#) or [10320/loc](#) : Landing-page URL.
- 21.11172/dateCreated: ISO 8601 creation timestamp.
- 21.11172/versionId: Opaque 160bit version identifier (or longer)
- 21.11172/digitalObjectPolicy: link/PID to the policy covering lifecycle rules (embargo, retention, access, tombstoning).

Recommended attributes are

- 21.11172/license: Link/PID to license (in case of publicly available data)
- 21.11172/dateModified: ISO 8601 timestamp of last modification
- 21.11172/authors: List of attributable authors of the data (not publishers or curators)
- 21.11172/citation: Recommended citation of this dataset.
- 21.11172/keywords: List of keywords.
- 21.11172/provenance: Link/PID to a provenance information
- 21.11172/versionTag: [SemVer 2.0.0](#) compliant version tag

Tombstoning is handled via the policy and landing page: PIDs never disappear. If an object is withdrawn, the PID resolves to a tombstone page stating what was removed, when and why, and, where available, the replacement PID (Weigel et al., 2018).

Authoritative metadata, landing pages, and record-type templates

The Handle record is intentionally thin. The landing page summarises the object for humans and links to its authoritative metadata and files, for example in LinkAhead. Inside LinkAhead, BatCAT applies a small project-wide baseline, minimal kernel includes: Owner/creator, title/name, creation date, version, license, provenance/source, related PIDs, with optional fields such as format and description. It could be said that changing e.g. kernel attributes is de facto an architectural change (affecting all platform). Rarely should happen.

Creation, validation, and use

Handle PIDs and Records should never be created manually. The DKMS based on LinkAhead will mint PIDs during the creation of LinkAhead Entities and create PID Records when an Entity is being published in the BatCAT Dataspace. As detailed in the sections [Consistency](#) and [Integrity](#), the consistency and integrity of the PID Records are partly guaranteed by design. However, the conformance with the BatCAT Profile is the responsibility of any agent creating or updating the Handle Record. LinkAhead's creation procedures are tested with detailed integration tests to ensure conformance with any configured FDO Profile. LinkAhead also provides an automated way to validate PID Records, even those which have not been created by LinkAhead, by just following the FDO Specifications (FDO Forum, 2024) and the Profile Definition.

Governance note. Profile changes are rare by design. Any update is treated as a major change under the metadata-change workflow (triage, review with ontology consultation where needed)

Versioning

Versioning in BatCAT ensures that changes to digital objects remain traceable and consistent across systems. Each object carries an opaque bit-valued version identifier and, if applicable, the link to a previous version. The version is recorded both in the PID record and on the landing page. Additionally, versions may be tagged as revisions using a strictly ordered versioning scheme, following [SemVer 2.0.0](#). While SemVer is originally intended to be used for software versioning (source code and/or compiled code), we apply it to datasets by defining the API of a dataset as the formatting and structure of the data – correcting errors in a data set would increase the patch version, adding data (e.g., appending rows to a table) or changing the structure in a backwards-compatible way (e.g., by appending a column to a table) would increase the minor version. Breaking changes (e.g., removing a column from a table and splitting it up into two new columns) would require a major version bump.

Tombstoning

Persistent identifiers remain resolvable even after withdrawal. If a digital object (or a version) is withdrawn, the PID resolves to a tombstone landing page that states:

- the object identifier/title
- its status = withdrawn
- the withdrawal date/time
- a brief reason/context where appropriate
- a replacement or successor PID, if available.
- The descriptive metadata remains accessible so that citations and provenance are preserved.

This is governed by the project’s PID policy is documented in public repository⁴

4. Metadata schema change workflow

The PID Profile in Sec. 3 stays minimal and stable but metadata schema and template changes must therefore be controlled, reviewed and documented. In this document “metadata schema” refers to the project-wide minimum templates used for ingest into LinkAhead and/or eLabFTW. This section (cf. Sec. 4) covers baseline project-wide metadata fields (i) (title/name, creator/owner, creation date, version, licence, provenance/source, related PIDs, optional description/format) and (ii) ontology mappings tied to those templates and any proposal to add, rename or reclassify any of these baseline fields are governed here. The following workflow governs changes to the minimum templates for ingest into LinkAhead/eLabFTW.

Figure 1: Metadata schema change workflow.

⁴ <https://github.com/HE-BatCAT/BatCAT-Dataewardship>

Metadata schema change workflow:

1. **Submit request:** A partner submits a short change request (either via the repository form (preferred) or by email).
2. **Triage (≤ 5 working days, SDO):** Within 5 working days, the SDO reviews the request, classifies it as minor or major, and tags the relevant Data Owner.
3. **Review/Decision:** The request is then assessed: it can be approved, sent back for clarification, or rejected with rationale.
4. **Implementation:** Once approved, implementation is ensured by the designated platform contact.
5. **Review check:** The SDO performs a final check; if the change alters the meaning of a field, the Ontology contact is also consulted.
6. **Release/Publish:** The update is released and made available to partners.
7. **Log and Notify:** A brief entry is added to the decision log, and all partners are notified of the outcome.

Timescale: Review and decision (triage, assessment, and final check) are targeted to be achieved within five working days each while technical implementation of approved changes by Platform Contacts should be completed within two weeks of approval. These timelines are indicative targets rather than rigid deadlines, inspired and aligned with earlier Horizon projects such as (VIMMP Consortium, 2021)

BatCAT ontologies: A set of ontologies developed within BatCAT, they contain all relevant concepts needed in the project, in particular to describe its use cases. By construction they are richer than the schema, in terms of the number of domain-specific entities (concepts, relations) they contain. They ensure interoperability beyond BatCAT (e.g., with other ontologies) and can be used as a source for additional metadata. The ontologies are written in Turtle (.TTL) format. Once completed, they will be public and available through a well-known dedicated repository, such as LOV-Linked Open Vocabularies⁵. The entity IRIs will be resolvable.

5. Sovereignty, data sharing, and data access

While the Handle PID System is responsible for making data findable and citable in general, the BatCAT DKMS is responsible for sharing data between partners of the consortium and for providing access to metadata and data for partners and external users. The PID Record will provide a pointer to the Landing Page of a data set which is a human-readable and machine-readable representation of the data and will inform any client e.g., browsers, indexers, and crawlers, which access mechanisms are provided and which authentication and authorization is required. The DKMS is responsible for providing the Landing Page in such an interoperable way.

Publicly available (meta-)data are accessible via HTTP endpoints serving HTML, JSON, and file downloads. In case of access-restricted data, human users need to login via Identity Management systems, e.g., via ORCID,

⁵ Linked Open Vocabularies ,LOV, <https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/> (Note: Accessed on 18 Sep 2025).

or, in the case of partners of the BatCAT consortium, the Identity Provider of their organization. Machine-actionable access is provided via the [Eclipse Dataspace Protocol](#) (DSP).

The DSP architecture ensures data sovereignty by leaving the point of policy enforcement under the control of the original data owners and providing peer-to-peer access between partners of the consortium and for external users. The DSP uses [ODLR](#) to define access rights. This allows data owners to enforce policies of various degrees, also including out-of-band mechanisms like signing legally binding data usage agreements (digitally or not) or grant time-restricted access. The DSP provides DCAT catalogs of data offers which again can be access-restricted or publicly available.

6. Consistency

Data **consistency** refers to the accuracy and reliability of data across a database or data storage system (Silberschatz, 2019); (Elmasri, Fundamentals of database systems, 2015). It ensures that data remains uniform and valid throughout its lifecycle, meaning that any changes made to the data are reflected consistently across all instances where that data is stored or accessed. This is crucial in maintaining the integrity of data, especially in environments where multiple users or systems interact with the same data.

Distributed systems face several challenges when it comes to maintaining data consistency. Here are some of the key challenges:

Challenge	Description
Network Partitioning	Network failures can lead to partitions where some nodes cannot communicate with others, making it difficult to ensure consistency.
Latency	The time it takes for data to propagate across the network can lead to stale data being read from different nodes.
Concurrent Updates	Multiple nodes may attempt to update the same data simultaneously, leading to conflicts and inconsistencies.
Replication Delays	Inconsistent states can arise if updates are not propagated to all replicas in a timely manner.
Data Versioning	Managing different versions of data across nodes can complicate consistency, especially when merging changes.
Fault Tolerance	Ensuring consistency in the presence of node failures or crashes adds complexity to the system design.

According to the CAP theorem (Elmasri, Fundamentals of Database Systems, 2016), a distributed system can only guarantee two of the three properties: Consistency, Availability, and Partition Tolerance, leading to trade-offs. Many distributed systems adopt eventual consistency (Elmasri, Fundamentals of Database Systems, 2016). For the scope of this document, the consistency of Handle PID Records and the data being stored in the DKMS and the consistency of data stored in different nodes of the BatCAT DKMS is most relevant.

In line with the RDA Recommendation on PID Kernel Information (Weigel, et al., 2019), “The PID KI record is a non-authoritative source for arbitrary metadata. If the information for an attribute duplicates metadata maintained elsewhere, the external source is the authority.” Thus, clients aiming for authoritative metadata must follow the references to the DKMS. As such, the PID handle record must include a reference to authoritative meta data. These clients must accept risks due to latency.

To avoid problems due to concurrent updates and versioning conflicts, PID Records should be created and updated automatically through the DKMS nodes which hold the authoritative data. If it is necessary to update PID Record manually, this should be handled by administrative staff of the DKMS (via the Platform Contacts) and only at the instigation of the SDO or the Data Contacts.

Overall, versioning of data is a mandatory mitigation strategy to avoid inconsistency to happen unnoticed. To allow replication and support fault tolerance, versions must be immutable and allow local validation. This is being guaranteed by adding a cryptographic hash and a RFC 3161 compliant trusted timestamp to the PID record. As such sensitive data and data subject to GDPR and other regulations must be kept out of the PID Record in all cases.

7. Integrity

Data **integrity** in data systems refers to the accuracy and reliability of data throughout its lifecycle. It ensures that data remains unaltered and valid, maintaining its intended meaning and quality. Data integrity is crucial for making informed decisions based on the data and is essential for compliance with regulations and standards.

At the DKMS level, data integrity is being guaranteed due to the ACID-compliance of the DKMS Nodes and the strict versioning of data sets. Integrity of the PID Records is guaranteed by implementing the recommendations of the FDO Forum (FDO Forum, 2024). Most importantly, PID Records should always be created automatically via the DKMS. The DKMS is based on the LinkAhead system⁶ which creates FDO-compliant PID Records. This allows to guarantee the following invariances (after El Masri, 2016):

- Entity Integrity: Each entity must have a unique identifier.
- Referential Integrity: A foreign key reference must always point to a valid record.
 - Attribute-Definition-PID must always point to a valid Attribute-Definition.
 - If Values are PID-References (as opposed to mere “links”), the reference must always point to a valid FDO.

⁶ <https://demo.indiscale.com/>

- This is being guaranteed by using trusted registries and/or immutable, replicated entities
- Domain Integrity: Each Value of must be consistent with the defined domain of the Attribute Definition. This is being achieved by relying on immutable attribute definitions.

This is a minimal set of invariances which can guarantee machine-actionable (PID Records FDO Forum, 2024). Integrity which goes beyond that cannot be guaranteed due to the distributed nature of the overall system of systems involving a distributed DKMS and Handle PID System.

8. Retention & deletion

To ensure consistent handling of data across BatCAT, this deliverable defines a Retention Playbook framework. The aim is to provide a common structure that partners can apply when specifying how long different categories of data should be kept and under which conditions they should be deleted. While the framework is established here, detailed values for each data type will be finalised in later phases of the project, once more datasets and workflows are available.

Retention Playbook framework

For each data type, the following elements are recorded:

- **Data type**
- **Where it is stored** (partner site, central node, etc.)
- **Retention period** (e.g. 3 months, 5 years, permanent)
- **Trigger event** that starts the retention clock (e.g. project end, dataset publication)
- **Responsible role** (partner Data Owner, central admin, etc.)

This framework ensures a transparent and harmonised approach across the consortium, while still allowing partners to adapt details to local requirements.

High-throughput data

BatCAT generates large volumes of temporary and raw data files. Keeping all of these permanently is neither feasible nor useful. To address this:

- Raw data files are kept locally and only for a limited period.
- Curated subsets (smaller, relevant data) are identified for longer retention.
- The central node stores metadata and previews, rather than complete raw files. This ensures that essential information is preserved without creating unnecessary storage burdens.

A complete Retention Playbook table will be developed as the project progresses. It will set retention periods, storage locations, and responsible roles for all major data types, providing a project-wide baseline for consistent retention and deletion practices.

9. Analysis of community recommendations

FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs), kernel information profiles, and application profiles in DCAT provide general mechanisms for structuring metadata. However, for materials science there is not yet a dedicated application profile group. Selecting certain metadata elements and placing detailed information inside the dataset description is therefore still an open issue. Ontologies can address this need, as they themselves can be treated as datasets.

W3C recommends having all as datasets as a list addressable by PIDs, each with their own landing page and metadata. The metadata is RDF, like JSON-LD. The information about the files is embedded in the metadata. If the dataset standard is W3C DCAT⁷, then any additions/requirements will turn it into an application profile of DCAT (i.e. remaining compatible). These may include any scientific information needed to make the metadata richer, such as new properties and their associated content, which may also be standardized.

Here are some relevant community recommendations regarding (1) FAIR, (2) EMMC, (3) RDA

- (1) FAIR, a set of implementation independent principles for qualifying the quality of data.
(Here we will go through the FAIR criteria one by one and say how we comply with them.)

FAIR has often become used as a “single” entity, while its origin and recommendations break down not only into the 4 elements of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable, but also into a number of specific indicators and recommendations for each of them^{8, 9}. We note the prime importance of persistent identifiers, e.g.

[F1. \(Meta\)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier](#)

[A1. \(Meta\)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol](#)

FAIR has been broken down by several research groups, e.g. FAIRsFAIR (F-UJI FAIR assessment tool) (Devaraju & Huber, 2025), into finer grain code addressing more specific concerns of how to test the codes¹⁰. This translated into the internal quality metric codes of the tool. However, some higher concerns affect several codes rather than one. Albeit FAIR principles are implementation independent any quality metrics/assessments are not. Summarized below for illustration:

F-UJI code	Very brief explanation	Implementation: DCAT in JSON-LD
F1	A Globally Unique Identifier (GUID) is used to identify resources including datasets and other artefacts. (This impacts IRIs if RDF is used)	IRIs containing UUID (internal) or hash string and Handle.net IRIs. Final IRI: <base>/dataset/uuid "@id": "UUID" "dcterms:identifier": [uuid, handle-iri]

⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat/>

⁸ [F1. \(Meta\)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier](#)

⁹ [A1. \(Meta\)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol](#)

¹⁰ <https://f-uji.net/index.php?action=methods>

F1	The identifiers must be persistent (in the sense of the scheme, not storage). Therefore, PIDs.	e.g. ORCiDs for people, DOI, RoR.org, and other standardised schemes. Other than these we may use our own PID scheme.
F2	Minimal metadata requirements. Aiming for rich metadata (and even richer is possible).	Kernel of core properties.
F3	PIDs used to map data, i.e. data files.	As a minimum MD5 to identify files. SHA-512 if there are antitampering requirements. We need to assign handle.net PIDs. Final IRI: <base>/distribution/uuid "@id": "MD5" "dcterms:identifier": [MD5, handle-iri]
F4	Data indexed in a searchable resource. (or at least deployable online)	Either the resources are readily deployable online, or we have a repository.
A1	Retrievable by ID using standard protocol.	Web protocols. e.g. HTTPS.
A1	Open and free communication protocol.	Web protocols. e.g. HTTPS.
A1	Protocol allows for authentication and authorisation.	Web protocols. e.g. HTTPS.
A2	Metadata is accessible even when data are no longer available (independent access).	IRIs for datasets and files work separately returning metadata and the files, respectively.
I1	It uses language for knowledge representation.	RDF (JSON-LD serialisation) and other ontologies. Using T4.4 knowledge.
I2	Vocabularies used are themselves FAIR.	RDF and other ontologies.
I3	It uses qualified references to other metadata.	Other metadata will have appropriate PIDs
R1	Richly described. Metadata with accurate and relevant attributes.	DCAT for datasets and other ontologies for anything else.
R1.1	Licensing)	Open licences stated via PIDs: IRIs from SPDX list. (ISO standard)
R1.2	Detailed provenance must be possible.	Using DCAT and PROV-O as a fallback.
R1.3	Both data and metadata meet community standards, i.e. domain needs.	Using T4.4 knowledge. We need to link the graph to other metadata by using the dataset ID or having a property for domain metadata.

We may now give further details using the codes.

JSON-LD good practices¹¹:

- Aliasing @id and @type into id and type
- Using aliases to avoid namespaces in the body of the object.
- The JSON-LD processor will create full IRIs using the information on the @context section.
- The dataset is the top object (the exemplar).

¹¹ <https://w3c.github.io/json-ld-bp/>

I2: (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles, which requires the vocabulary used for the metadata to at least be documented and resolvable using globally unique and **persistent identifiers**. (Note: It is a requirement for FAIR to have domain-specific metadata and use established metadata standards. See therefore also below. Therefore, use of domain-specific metadata must, to some extent, be mandatory.)

FAIR DO what is our position, will add a few words.

(2) EMMC

EMMC has been aiming to address the lack of relevant metadata in the materials modelling (and with EMCC also characterisation) communities. The resulting¹² [MODA \(Modelling Data\) and CHADA \(Chararcterisation Data\)](#) terminology and metadata agreements (documented in CEN Workshop Agreements), serve to fill that gap. BatCAT re-uses, or refers to, MODA and CHADA for metadata and relevant conceptualisations from battery and characterization domain ontologies in Task 4.4. This is inspiring our eLabFTW templates, and templates for data ingest into LinkAhead.

We will ingest >10 000 data points from modelling and simulation, and there, the MODA tabular metadata structure can be a basis for what information we will be ingesting; we are not following it exactly, but to the extent that it is found to be helpful; there we can also use the OSMO ontology. The following will be taken from RoMM/MODA/OSMO as mandatory fields:

- Level of modelling (electronic, atomistic, mesoscopic, continuum)
- What type of modelling (high-level classification of physical equations)

We can have some more from MODA as optional information.

Building on these, the [EMMO](#)¹³ ontology, developed in several projects, is under EMMC governance and aims to provide not only an upper and middle level ontology framework for materials science and engineering applications, but also discipline and domain ontologies and taxonomies based on standards as much as possible. Also CHAMEO (ontology version of CHADA) will be used for semantic interoperability purposes.

(3) Research Data Alliance (RDA)

A currently active RDA Working Group¹⁴ on has compiled a "[Field Guide for individuals who are supporting the materials science and engineering community to increase the FAIR maturity of their data \(data stewards\)](#)" which provides recommendations for each step of the Data Management Life Cycle, as reproduced below

¹² [MODA \(Modelling Data\) and CHADA \(Chararcterisation Data\)](#)

¹³ [EMMO](#)

¹⁴ [Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains](#)

Figure 2: A data lifecycle model shown with crosscutting concerns of the FAIR data principles.

In the context of BatCAT we note in particular the provenance recommendations³ and the importance of persistent identifiers for samples, as for all records and digital objects in general.

For PIDs, the pertinent RDA recommendations (Weigel, DiLauro, & Zastrow, 2015) are:

For explanation, we quote from (Weigel, et al., 2019) “PID Kernel Information is a set of attributes stored within the PID record, i.e., information stored at a global or local PID registry and accessible by a resolver. The primary purpose of PID Kernel Information is in support of smart machine actionable decisions that can be accomplished through inspection of the PID record alone.” Note that a resolver is a globally available infrastructure system that has the capability to resolve a PID into useful, current state information describing the properties of a Digital Object. The Handle PID service used by BatCAT is able to utilise PID Kernel information.

10. Managing and publishing governance specifications

BatCAT makes its data stewardship governance actionable by (i) publishing the mandatory metadata kernels and governance artefacts in a public location, and (ii) ensuring a time-bounded metadata change process where every approved update is logged. To ensure transparency, all core artefacts are publicly available and maintained under version control in the BatCAT governance repository.

The following artefacts are maintained and versioned for project use:

- metadata schema-change workflow,
- PID and landing-page policy (including tombstoning),
- BatCAT Handle Record Profile (PID Kernel Information),
- Retention Playbook, and
- minimum metadata kernels.

All governance documents are made available in the public BatCAT governance repository, which serves as the reference for this document¹⁵. Most artefacts are provided in Markdown format, while the minimum metadata kernels are also supplied in YAML to enable structured and machine-actionable reuse. Where applicable, future tagged releases will include additional machine-readable companions such as JSON-LD templates, RDF/TTL mappings, or YAML/JSON examples, accompanied by release notes documenting approved changes.

To operationalise these specifications, BatCAT defines a minimum DCAT-compatible metadata set per record type. This baseline is expressed in community-standard formats and aligned with established frameworks: the FAIR principles (Wilkinson, et al., 2016), MODA/CHADA, PROV-O¹⁶, and SPDX¹⁷. The PID kernel remains intentionally minimal in the Handle record to guarantee stability, while the authoritative metadata resides on the landing page or platform and can be exported in interoperable formats such as JSON-LD.

11. References

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¹⁵ <https://github.com/HE-BatCAT/BatCAT-DataStewardship>

¹⁶ W3C. (2013). *PROV-O: The PROV Ontology*. World Wide Web Consortium (W3C Recommendation). <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

¹⁷ ISO/IEC. (2021). *Software Package Data Exchange (SPDX™), Version 2.2.1*. ISO/IEC 5962:2021. International Organization for Standardization. Available at: <https://spdx.dev>

12. Annex

Annex Table 1: RDA Kernel Information profile

	Property identifier	Content format	Cardinality	Explanation
1	PID	Handle	1..n	Global identifier for the object; external to the PID Kernel Information
2	KernelInformationProfile	Handle	1	Handle to the Kernel Information type profile; serves as pointer to profile in DTR. Address of DTR federation expected to be global (common) knowledge.
3	digitalObjectType	Handle	1	Handle points to type definition in DTR for this type of object. Distinguishing metadata from data objects is a client decision within a particular usage context, which may to some extent rely on the digitalObjectType value provided.
4	digitalObjectLocation	URL	1..n	Pointer to the content object location (pointer to the DO). This may be in addition to a pointer to a human-readable landing page for the object.
5	digitalObjectPolicy	Handle	1	Pointer to a policy object which documents changes to the object or its Kernel Information record, including particularly object access and modification policies. A caller should be able to determine the expected future changes to the object from the policy, which are based on managed processes the object owner maintains.
6	etag	Hex string	1	Checksum of object contents. Checksum format determined via attribute type referenced in a Kernel Information record.
7	dateModified	ISO 8601 Date	0..1	Last date/time of object modification. Mandatory if applicable.
8	dateCreated	ISO 8601 Date	1	Date/time of object creation
9	version	String	0..1	If tracked, a version for the object, which must follow a total order. Mandatory for all objects with at least one predecessor version.
10	wasDerivedFrom	Handle	0..n	P ROV-DM : Transformation of an entity into another, an update of an entity resulting in a new one, or the construction of a new entity based on a pre-existing entity.

Source: Weigel et al. (2019), CC BY 4.0, doi:10.15497/rda00031.